

Cover

Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic *in silico* drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility

<p><i>When citing, sharing, or adapting this work, please provide proper attribution as follows:</i></p>	<p>Flora T. Musuamba, Ine Skottheim Rusten, Raphaëlle Lesage, Giulia Russo, Roberta Bursi, Luca Emili, Gaby Wangorsch, Efthymios Manolis, Kristin E. Karlsson, Alexander Kulesza, Eulalie Courcelles, Jean-Pierre Boissel, Cécile F. Rousseau, Emmanuelle M. Voisin, Rossana Alessandrello, Nuno Curado, Enrico Dall'ara, Blanca Rodriguez, Francesco Pappalardo, Liesbet Geris. <i>Scientific and regulatory evaluation of mechanistic in silico drug and disease models in drug development: Building model credibility</i>. CPT Pharmacometrics Syst Pharmacol. 2021; 00: 1– 22. https://doi.org/10.1002/psp4.12669</p> <p>https://ascpt.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/psp4.12669</p>
<p><i>Abstract</i></p>	<p>The value of <i>in silico</i> methods in drug development and evaluation has been demonstrated repeatedly and convincingly. While their benefits are now unanimously recognized, international standards for their evaluation, accepted by all stakeholders involved, are still to be established. In this white paper, we propose a risk-informed evaluation framework for mechanistic model credibility evaluation. To properly frame the proposed verification and validation activities, concepts such as context of use, regulatory impact and risk-based analysis are discussed. To ensure common understanding between all stakeholders, an overview is provided of relevant <i>in silico</i> terminology used throughout this paper. To illustrate the feasibility of the proposed approach, we have applied it to three real case examples in the context of drug development, using a credibility matrix currently being tested as a quick-start tool by regulators. Altogether, this white paper provides a practical approach to model evaluation, applicable in both scientific and regulatory evaluation contexts.</p>